

IMPACT OF GLOBALIZATION ON THE ENGLISH LANGUAGE IN THE MODERN EDUCATIONAL SPACE

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ABSTRACT

The article examines the main characteristics and role of the globalization process in the modern world, as well as its connection with the English language, which occupies the place of the language of world communication in the XXI century.

KEYWORDS

Globalization, English, global English, intercultural communication, international culture, an international language.

Globalization is considered one of the social phenomena of the information society, the peculiarity of which is the disappearance of barriers and the emergence of interethnic cultures. It is considered a historical phenomenon of the modern era and is understood as a series of processes that make up the unity of the world. In the XXI century, a person has every reason to be proud of his achievements. Significant political, economic, social, demographic and cultural changes are taking place in the modern world. Technological progress has accelerated the pace of globalization, and development, competition, interconnection and cooperation have become key features of the international economy and foreign policy. Economic, political and ideological borders between the countries began to blur, and the process of world integration began, inspiring hope and faith in establishing peace and maintaining stability in relations. However, the future of an interdependent world remains uncertain. Whether the idea of community and cooperation of nations coexisting in a world without barriers will become a reality, and whether we will eventually be able to come to international solidarity, depends on how relations between peoples and countries are built and how great the potential for communication in the world community [1].

Several urgent problems faced by modern man in the XXI century, such as global warming, ecology, the fight against AIDS, terrorism, and drug trafficking, are becoming millennium problem that requires a "global approach" in perception and thinking, as well as "global" responses. It is quite difficult to deny the fact that scientific and technological progress and the development of a modern communication system

are taking place against the background of the rapid spread of the English language around the world. Today it is the most popular language among students. It is also worth noting its dominant role in the field of science, where 70-80% of all publications are published in English. English is the official language of most international organizations and has official status in countries around the world. None of the existing languages has such a privileged status in the EU as English, although within this organization there is an official policy of ensuring equal status for all official languages of the EU. Only English is the language of contact between people speaking different languages [2]. Currently, English has already established itself as the lingua franca, the language of international communication. An international language is a language that can be used to communicate by a significant number of people around the world. [3] In ancient times, ancient Greek was an international language, then for more than a thousand years, Latin was the most important international language used for international communication in all spheres of human life. Negotiations were conducted on it, trade deals were concluded, and scientific papers were written. In the XVI-XVII centuries, Spanish was used as an international language. At the beginning of the XVIII century, French became the most important language of international communication in Europe. In the XIX century, the German language also acquired great importance due to the high achievements of German scientists of that time. In parallel, English and Spanish were developing as international languages, thanks to the colonies of these countries scattered around the world [4]. At the end of the XX century, English became the most important international language. Now thousands of newspapers and magazines of recent years are full of headlines of this kind. This statement seems so obvious that most of us are unlikely to dispute its validity. English is the language of international communication. All over the world, English is becoming the language of popular publications, international business and diplomacy, scientific conferences, sports arena, popular music, cinema and advertising. In modern society, it is in greater demand than ever before in history. Proficiency in this language opens up huge opportunities for those who want to keep up with the times. The uniqueness of the situation also lies in the fact that the number of people using it as a foreign language is significantly more than native speakers (currently this ratio is 3:1). So, it can be argued that the English language largely provides access to the treasury of world knowledge, especially in areas such as science and technology, and this is the basis of education. The reason why in recent years many countries have given English the status of an official language or have chosen it as the main foreign language in their schools is the possibility of getting a good education. Since the 60s, English has been taught at universities in many countries. Since most students are constantly confronted with

monographs and periodicals in English, it would be advisable to train them to better prepare them for this work. In many cases, teachers also face a multilingual audience since universities and colleges are constantly increasing the intake of international students. All this speaks in favour of English as the most common language of international communication. It would be a mistake to believe that the globalization of the English language is the result solely of economic and political superiority. It is necessary to pay attention to the peculiarities of the English language, which predetermined its victory in a kind of race for world linguistic dominance. Firstly, it is the richness and depth of the lexical composition. The 20-volume Oxford Dictionary of Modern English includes more than 615 thousand words (for comparison, the 20-volume Large Academic Dictionary of the Russian language contains about 215 thousand words). Taking into account scientific and technical terminology, the total lexical composition of the English language will exceed one million words, which makes it the largest in the world. According to some estimates, the vocabulary of the English language is currently being actively replenished with new words: from 8000 to 20,000 lexical units annually. In general, about 200,000 English words are used, which is at least 2 times more than words, for example, German, Russian or French. The presence of a large number of synonyms, and the phrasal and idiomatic richness of the English language contain the potential to express a variety of meanings and solve any communicative tasks - from everyday communication to high poetry. Secondly, English has an important quality of flexibility. Flexibility manifests itself at different levels of the language system. The word order, the accompanying category, the possibility of using the same word as a noun and verb, and large derivational possibilities - all this works for the flexibility of the English language as a communicative tool. Thirdly, the grammar of the English language has a higher degree of unification than most languages of the world. For example, the gender category is completely conveyed by the word and does not require additional manifestation using articles, as in German or Spanish. A predicate can easily do without a subject. The case forms of nouns in English are practically absent (except for some personal pronouns), which, compared, for example, with Finnish, which has fifteen forms for each noun, or Russian with its 12 forms, is an example of the highest degree of grammatical unification of the system. The same should be said about the verb: if, for example, in Latin, the verb had 120 possible forms, and in modern German - 16, then English operates with only 5 forms, of which only 3 are actively used. Fourth, English is considered relatively simple in terms of spelling and pronunciation: it does not require mastering subtle tonal variations of pronunciation, like Cantonese, nor a bizarre, sometimes to the point of extravagance, the combination of consonants, like Welsh or

Gaelic. Of course, English includes some sounds that are usually difficult for foreigners to pronounce or sounds that have many possible variants of graphic fixation. However, the relative phonetic and graphical simplicity of the English language is supported by regularity in the pronunciation of consonants and freedom from diacritics of vowels and consonants. In addition, borrowings from foreign words in English, as a rule, retain the original spelling. Phonetic predictability of graphic transmission in English is quite high (84% [5]), while those who know Latin but do not know English are unpredictable in pronunciation, will write no more than 3% of English words (those about which English learners playfully say: "write Manchester - read Liverpool"). Fifthly, the globalization of the English language is facilitated by its cosmopolitan nature: it actively accepts thousands of words from other languages with which it has historically come into contact, which gives it a sense of closeness and accessibility, a kind of linguistic hospitality, unlike languages such as, for example, French, which does everything possible to prevent other languages from influencing him, - this is an extreme manifestation of linguistic. The linguistic factors of the attractiveness of the English language listed above are of great importance for obtaining global status, but they cannot provide it without well-known extra-linguistic factors: technological, political and economic. Therefore, even though in the modern world English as a global language is in an impregnable position, its future as such is not necessarily guaranteed. In the Middle Ages, Latin seemed to have established itself forever as the universal language of education and culture. He seemed unchanged but changed. First of all, it should be remembered that among the languages of international communication, there have historically been contenders for worldwide distribution, but their claims, however, did not go beyond the territories of multinational state entities (Roman, Byzantine, Mongolian, and French empires). Many scientists reasonably claim that in the fields of business, science, computer science, education, transport, politics, sports, entertainment and mass consumption, English has become a global language of interethnic communication [6]. Moreover, it is not only a source but also an intermediary for the export of lexical units and grammatical constructions. In addition, it is important to take into account that the fact of fluency in English today is not as important for linguistic globalization as the fact of its active use. For comparison, the most widely spoken language in the world - the Mandarin dialect of Chinese - has about 1 billion native speakers, and English - has about 400 million, but according to the British Council, about 2 billion more people regularly use English (not being native speakers). In addition, global Internet communication, the main tool of which has historically been the English language, inexorably expands the composition of the "users" of the global language. When representatives of the "gadget generation" make

up the majority of the world's population, the consequences of these trends will worsen. Signs of this can still be seen today. For example, the UN currently uses five official languages: English, French, Spanish, Russian and Chinese, but about 90% of international organizations use English as at least one of their official languages (while French already makes up less than 50%). Moreover, about a third of international organizations (OPEC, ASEAN, etc.) use English exclusively as the official language, and this figure is growing - more than 90% among Asian international organizations. To understand the prospects for the development of a global language, it is necessary to take into account the opposition of two trends - towards the universalization of instruments of intercultural interaction, on the one hand, and the preservation of national identity, on the other. The dominance of an external language or culture can lead to a negative reaction. Although most of the former British colonies retained English as their official language after independence, discontent with the cultural dominance of English is growing in some countries. Paradoxically, the latter trend is especially noticeable in the United States (the quantitative growth of the Latin American population, the formalization of the Spanish status in some states, etc.) with their dominance in economic, technical and political terms. It is the United States that is the driving force of the English language in the modern world. However, if the United States loses its dominant position in these areas, the linguistic loyalty of other countries may decrease significantly until it is replaced by a new dominant force. And here we encounter another paradox. The only possible candidate to compete with the United States in technological and economic (but not political) aspects in the foreseeable future is China. But China is one of the most active exploiters of the global English language [6]. The increase in the number of people who speak English to one degree or another has reached a historical maximum of 2 billion, mainly due to the population of India and China. Perhaps that is why the long-term future of English as a global language is in the hands of Asia. The latter partly explains why Chinese, whose main dialect (Mandarin) is spoken by about a billion people, is far from the status of not only global but also sub-global. At the same time, the key to the stability of the global status of the English language is the fact that this language has become the main tool of Internet communication, which today involves more than 5 billion people who cannot do without knowledge of the Latin alphabet and a minimum set of several dozen words that make up the vocabulary of a modern Internet user, starting with the most common globalism-ok (okay, OK). It should be noted that, although the coincidence of some extra-linguistic factors was important for obtaining the global status of the English language, linguistic factors themselves were crucial for maintaining this status. The fact of American influence in the modern world cannot be denied. The

globalization of trade, the economy and the spread of the American way of life - what is called "Americanization" - contributed to the development of American English. Having become the world language of entertainment, business, and science, American English laid the foundation for the further expansion of American culture. Global markets and a global entertainment and travel network are followed by global communication in an international language. Again, it is permeated through and through with American national characteristics, which cannot always be understood and accepted by other people. E-mail and the Internet are used all over the world today, and it is undoubtedly a very convenient, fast and effective means of communication. Only one "but": people in different countries are forced to adapt to the language and features of electronic means of communication, which were created, of course, for the English language. To communicate in another language, they have to resort to various technical tricks. For example, superscript characters adopted in different European languages cannot be used in most mail programs, the same applies to non-Latin alphabets (Russian, Greek, Chinese, Japanese, etc.). In addition, "fast English" has its etiquette and standards of politeness, which many are horrified by. For example, the standard "best wishes" and "warm wishes" automatically placed at the end of letters simply cannot be accepted by those for whom English is not their native language. Worse, all these communication innovations are shared by people. Even with traditional methods of communication (for example, face-to-face meetings, telephone conversations), non-native speakers always find themselves in a more difficult situation. It is not only English that is difficult. The difference in cultures and mentalities is an additional obstacle. Non-native speakers continue to think in their native language, trying to express the specifics of their thinking in English. And he's not always perfect for it. The efforts of a person trying to communicate in a foreign language should at least be appreciated and supported. A native speaker should be aware that he is in a better position and help his foreign interlocutor: speak slowly, articulate clearly, choose the right words, and avoid slang, jargon and complex sentences. 66 In conclusion, we can say that, although today English can be considered the language of international communication or a global language, we cannot say with absolute certainty that it can hold these positions and strengthen them. Therefore, thinking about the future of the English language as a world language, we must analyze some patterns and trends that may interfere with this phenomenon [7]. There are situations when residents of the country experience such a hostile attitude to the English language that they refuse to give it the status of an official or first foreign language. Such an attitude arises as a reaction to the protection of one's language - a symbol of national identity and individuality. Most people have a natural desire to

speak their native language, to see its further development. Imposing the language of another culture does not cause them positive emotions. Many peoples associate English with the colonial period when society despised local languages. If a certain number of countries take such a position, then the decision on assigning the status of the world language to English will be very problematic. Nevertheless, the influence of the English language in the world is great and continues to grow every year.

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